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ISSUES RELATED TO TEACHING ENGLISH AT SMART SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN: ENGLISH FOR STEAM

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***Abstract:** the article discusses issues related to teaching English at SMART schools in Uzbekistan, and intends to suggest effective ways to implement novel language course "English for STEAM".*

***Keywords:** teaching English, smart school, STEAM, Uzbekistan*

During the years of independence, as in all areas of the country, there have been major reforms and upgrades in the field of education. In particular, The Law "On Education" and the "National Program for Personnel Training" were adopted on August 29, 1997, to form a competent generation in the process of education, by improving their independent thinking, creative mind, strong willful. As a result, the legal basis for educating and vocational training of citizens has been created and the constitutional right "everyone has the right to learn" has been strengthened. Special attention was paid to the study of foreign languages in order to integrate the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the experience of the best world nations, to ensure closer cooperation with leading foreign educational institutions and training of competent staff. In particular, the Decree of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On measures for further improvement of foreign languages learning» (December 10, 2012) is a key factor for modernization of teaching foreign languages at all stages, in which the importance of teaching and learning English across the country were pointed out. Taking account of this directive document the competence-based teaching was implemented in the Uzbekistan system of FLT [1;7]. Due to this decree, the work on learning and teaching foreign languages, especially English, was promoted to a new stage in the republic education system. Nowadays, pupils who are studying in the new generation of textbooks and educational technology, created with the result of this important document, are being taught in Grade 7 at schools. It is assumed that in the next five years, we can see a positive outcome of this important stage. However, the age of the XXI century — the high technology and the age of intellectual generation, put forward a number of huge critical tasks ahead of the education system of each country. Particularly, the development of modern science, training of competent personnel who mastered foreign languages, the effective use of advanced pedagogical technologies, the use of ICT in education and various technological achievements, and most importantly, to bring up the creative-minded younger generation are the instances of the requirement of the modern age. [2;1] To

carry out such tasks, first of all, it is necessary to build modern smart schools equipped with the necessary material and technical base.

According to researchers, "The smart school is a technology-based teaching-learning institution for preparing children with the effective functioning of smart school which requires skilled staff, and well-designed teaching, learning and supporting processes. It encourages active thinking process while its environment motivates students to use personal computers (PCs), the internet, and intranets as research and communication tools. Students are able to access online libraries, use electronic mail (e-mail) or combination of desktop video-conferencing and chat rooms for doing tutorials" [3;3]

For the same purpose, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Measures for the Establishment of Presidential Schools" (PR-4199) was adopted on February 20, 2019. According to this document, during 2019-2021 years, the Presidential schools in the form of a specialized state general education institution will be established in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the regions and the city of Tashkent. These educational institutions will carry out a deep study of natural and exact sciences, foreign languages, engineering, and information technology and will provide the creation of all conditions for the development of innovative skills and development of students. [4;1-2] It is noteworthy that these SMART schools have a special emphasis on the learning process, based on the technology of STEAM, in which school subjects are taught in English language. In this way, it is preferable to understand the concept of STEAM technology, "STEAM stands for Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Math. Each of STEAM's five subjects shares a common approach and focus. They require gathering and using evidence to create knowledge or solve problems. STEAM learning happens naturally every day as children explore, play, and try new things. When pupils have the opportunity to investigate the world around them, they learn and experiment with new STEAM skills and theories. Research shows there is a positive relationship between STEAM experiences and future success in school." [5;1] STEAM subjects are not a new concept. The revolutionary step forward is the approach to how these subjects are being explored in schools. Project-based, collaborative, and hands-on experiential learning is taking kids out of the textbook and proving to them with tangible experiences and understanding of how the skills they're learning will impact the world around them. Indeed, STEAM technology is becoming one of the most widespread teaching technologies as "according to the Bureau of Labor Statistics, there were nearly 8.6 million STEAM jobs in May 2015, a total of 6.2% of U.S. employment. The U.S. Department of Education reports that the number of STEAM jobs in the United States will continue to grow, and are expected to increase 14% from 2010 to 2020. This is nearly three times higher than the national average of 5-

8% across all other job sectors” [6;3] It should be noted that the advantages of STEAM technology in the formation of modern comprehensively advanced generation in our country are numerous. However, the creation of the Presidential Schools' educational system based on the technology of STEAM in Uzbekistan creates a number of difficulties and challenges to the students and teachers. In particular,

- Language basis for a holistic education that focuses on thinking skills, effective communication skills, cognitive, effective and social development;
- integration of living skills' knowledge, language, and moral values;
- integration of a multi-disciplinary and inter-disciplinary curriculum through the use of English;
- integration of technology as a tool in the teaching and learning process;
- difficulty supporting productive language collaboration among students.

Therefore, Adults can foster children’s development of STEAM skills by providing learning opportunities and materials that support exploration and discovery in order to lessen the negative impact of STEAM in Uzbekistan Presidential schools. Because STEAM activities are interactive and exploration-based, they provide many opportunities for children who are dual language learners to be actively involved. In addressing the aforementioned problems, it is desirable to develop the English for STEAM methodology, covering vital areas and providing them an insight into interactive games, puzzles, and other materials. This methodology is intended to include:

Of course, at first glance, the fields of science may seem to be a great deal for the students. However, this sophisticated process can be facilitated with interactive collaborative games, real-life environment, active engagement of pupils, and teacher's support for them with necessary opportunities. Now, we will observe an interactive lesson called "Is the Earth getting warmer?" for one of the content subjects of SCIENCE (S of STEAM) — Geoscience.

For the last several years, scientists have been asking "Is the Earth getting warmer?" In the classroom, pupils will investigate this question by observing a global warming experiment. After looking at the data from the experiment, pupils will make an educated guess about why the world is getting warmer and develop a definition for the term climate change. In addition, they will learn how to preview texts and practice some language used to make comparisons when talking about global warming and climate change. When pupils investigate their environment, they experience the satisfaction that can come from investigation, discovery, and solving problems. Teachers can foster their development of Geoscience knowledge by providing learning opportunities and materials that support exploration and discovery. Consequently, during the well-established classroom environment, pupils can be expected to:

- Observe an experiment of global warming through OHP or PCs;
- Analyze the data of an experiment to draw conclusions at the end of the lesson;
- Preview texts related to the topic;
- Use comparative adjectives in writing judgments;
- Develop a definition for the term climate change;
- Define and accurately use content-related vocabulary in course activities and games;
- Read, watch, and listen to a variety of texts and multimedia sources;
- Demonstrate their understanding of these materials and key course ideas through a discussion board and peer-reviewed written assessment.

In conclusion, the language teaching staff use when they engage with schoolchildren can encourage creative thinking, reflection, and problem-solving. By observing, listening, and responding to pupils' interests, teachers support their curiosity. When given the chance to communicate their thoughts and ideas, pupils develop their own thinking. "It is reasonable that young people should be in constant contact with persons of their age abroad in the fields of science, culture, business, sports, and others. This creates a great opportunity for them to demonstrate their capacities globally. ... We will continue to focus our attention on deeper teaching of English and other foreign languages as a priority... [Sh. M.Mirziyoyev, President's address to the Parliament of the Republic of Uzbekistan — Oliy Majlis. 22 December

2017]” That is why, English for STEAM in Presidential SMART schools revolves around problem-solving and the scientific method: observing, asking questions, making predictions, experimenting, and discussing. It is important for teaching staff to model this process so that pupils become familiar with the steps involved in solving problems.

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